

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVED METHODOLOGY FOR OPTIMIZING THE PROCESS OF RECOVERING MILITARY EQUIPMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF COMBAT OPERATIONS

Baranov Yu.,

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, professor of the Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Baranov A.,

Candidate of Technical Sciences (Ph.D), Associate Professor, associate professor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Brychynskiy O.,

Senior instructor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Kolotelo P.,

Instructor of the Support Forces Tactics Department, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Malinovskiy N.

Senior instructor of the Department of Engineering Equipment, Hetman Petro Sahaidachnyi National Army Academy, Ukraine, Lviv

Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of military equipment (ME) at the proper level in the conditions of carrying out combat operations (CO).

On the basis of the existing model of automotive technical support for the process of recovering vehicles damaged in combat, for the construction of which the apparatus of discrete Markov processes was used, a methodology for optimizing the process of recovering vehicles in the conditions of carrying out combat operations was developed. The peculiarities of the developed methodology are the possibility of taking into account the determination of the optimal term for ME recovery, which does not coincide with the term of its use for the intended purpose in the conditions of carrying out combat operations.

Keywords: military equipment; maintenance; technical condition; combat operations.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Equipping the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine with technically serviceable ME is the main condition for successful warfare. It is clear that the failure of ME samples in the conditions of carrying out combat operations occurs both due to combat damage and operational and technical malfunctions, as a result of the increased intensity of operation of ME samples in these conditions. Studies related to the management of TC and the recovery of ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations are becoming increasingly relevant. This is due to the presence of a sufficiently large number of ME in the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine for various combat purposes.

Formulation of the problem. Based on the existing model of automotive support for the process of recovery of automotive equipment damaged in combat [1-3], in particular, using the calculation relations that describe the main states of the recovery system, it is proposed to improve the methodology for optimizing the process of ME recovery in the conditions of carrying out combat operations. The existing model is based on the apparatus of discrete Markov processes that allows determining and comparing the probabilities of ME being in each of its states, which are most important for solving the main tasks of managing ME TC in the conditions of carrying out combat operations.

It is known that during the recovery of an object's

working capacity, this process is influenced by many factors that are not only poorly coordinated but also accompanied by uncertainty of a random, natural, and antagonistic nature. Therefore, the appropriate way out of this situation is to reduce the dimensionality of the analysis problem by comparing and ranking the recovery tasks by some generalized indicator. Let's suppose the probabilities of the ME being in each state in the conditions of carrying out combat operations.

Analysis of recent research and publications.

Issues related to maintaining the serviceable TC of ME samples are revealed in the works of national specialists and scientists, in particular: P. Openko [4], O. Volokh [5], N. Shaptalenko [6], O. Vorobyov [7] and others, that reveal most of the issues of this problem in depth.

The purpose of the article. An improved technique for optimizing the process of ME recovery in the conditions of carrying out combat operations

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

It is not difficult to imagine a situation where it is necessary to perform maintenance of ME after its preparation for operation or after its combat use, as well as a situation where the combat use of ME has shown the need for its new preparation for use. For example, taking into account the unsatisfactory results of combat support due to insufficiently thorough preliminary preparation. Let's assume the following variant of the states and transitions of ME during its use as intended

(Fig. 1).

It is important to emphasize that this graph contains cyclic (not one-time) transitions, and reflects the actual transitions of ME to a particular state. For example, the transition to the state of combat use of ME is

possible after its preparation, after maintenance, and after the recovery of a damaged ME. The state of recovery of damaged equipment is also possible after its combat use, and after its preparation, for the purpose of its use, and after its maintenance.

Figure 1 - Variant of states and transitions of military equipment during its use for the intended purpose: P_{Π} – the state of preparation of ME for use; P_3 – the state of combat use of ME; P_B – the state of recovery of ME after its damage; P_O – the state of maintenance of ME before or after COs; a, A – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of preparation of ME for use to the state of its maintenance; b, B – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of maintenance of ME to the state of its combat use; c, C – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of combat use of ME to the state of its maintenance; d, D – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of maintenance of ME to the state of its recovery after damage; e, E – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of preparation of ME for use to the state of its recovery after damage; f, F – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of preparation of ME to the state of its combat use; g, G – the intensity and probability of transitions of ME from the state of combat use to the state of its preparation for use; h, H – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of recovery of ME after damage to the state of its combat use; i, I – the intensity and probability of transitions from the state of combat use of the vehicle to the state of its recovery after damage.

The purpose of the proposed methodology is to optimize the recovery of ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations, in which the values of quality indicators of TC management reach a certain level, namely: the coefficient of technical readiness K_{TT} , unreadiness K_{HT} of ME for their intended use and the minimax criterion E_{\min}^{\max} .

Necessary initial data for the calculation, constraints and assumptions.

In the process of using ME for its intended purpose in the conditions of carrying out CO over time, it is in any state with probabilities:

$P_{\Pi}(t)$ – the probability of ME being in the state of preparation for its use;

$P_3(t)$ – probability of ME being in the state of intended use;

$P_B(t)$ – the probability of ME being in the state of recovery after its damage;

$P_O(t)$ – the probability of ME being in the state of maintenance.

Upon completion of any type of recovery work, the original properties of the object are fully recovered, the term of the next maintenance is rescheduled, and the entire maintenance process is repeated. At the same time, we will assume that no scheduled repairs are carried out during the period of operation under consideration.

Analytical dependencies for calculating the optimal values of military equipment recovery indicators.

A set of differential equations describing the process of ME being in each of the 4 states is expedient to write, according to the rule of contours for the graph of transitions of the ME recovery system in the conditions

of carrying out combat operations, in the environment of each of the states of this system (see Fig. 1) in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dP_{II}(t)}{dt} &= gGP_3 - (fF + aA + eE)P_{II}; \\ \frac{dP_3(t)}{dt} &= fFP_{II} + bBP_O + hHP_B - (gG + cC + iI)P_3; \\ \frac{dP_B(t)}{dt} &= dDP_O + eEP_{II} + iP_{II} + hHP_B; \\ \frac{dP_O(t)}{dt} &= aAP_{II} + cCP_3 - (bB + dD)P_O. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Solving the differential equations (1) leads to the following system of algebraic equations:

$$P_{II}(t) = [gGP_3] \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(fF + aA + eE)t]\}}{fF + aA + eE}; \tag{2}$$

$$P_3(t) = [fFP_{II} + bBP_O + hHP_B] \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(gG + cC + iI)t]\}}{gG + cC + iI}; \tag{3}$$

$$P_B(t) = [dDP_O + eEP_{II} + iP_{II}] \frac{\{1 - \exp[-hHt]\}}{hH}; \tag{4}$$

$$P_O(t) = [aAP_{II} + cCP_3] \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(bB + dD)t]\}}{bB + dD}. \tag{5}$$

The condition for normalizing the total probability of the system states (it characterizes the complete group of phenomena) for the time $t \geq 0$ is the equation

$$P_{II}(t) + P_3(t) + P_B(t) + P_O(t) = 1. \tag{6}$$

After complex transformations (2-5), taking into account (6) (in order to solve a system of five algebraic equations containing four unknown quantities), we obtain the probabilities of ME being in the conditions of carrying out combat operations in the corresponding states: "preparation of ME for the purpose of its use"; "use of ME for its intended purpose"; "recovery of ME after damage"; "maintenance of ME" in the form:

$$P_{II}(t) = \frac{\zeta dD}{1 + \alpha + (\alpha\beta + \gamma)/(1 - \psi i I \eta h H) + \zeta dD}; \tag{7}$$

$$P_3(t) = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha + (\alpha\beta + \gamma)/(1 - \psi i I \eta h H) + \zeta dD}; \tag{8}$$

$$P_B(t) = \frac{(\alpha\beta + \gamma)/(1 - \psi i I \eta h H)}{1 + \alpha + (\alpha\beta + \gamma)/(1 - \psi i I \eta h H) + \zeta dD}; \tag{9}$$

$$P_O(t) = \frac{\alpha}{1 + \alpha + (\alpha\beta + \gamma)/(1 - \psi i I \eta h H) + \zeta dD}. \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{де } \alpha &= \xi(aA\zeta gG + cC); \quad \xi = \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(bB + dD)t]\}}{bB + dD}; \quad \beta = \psi(dD + iI\eta bB); \\ \psi &= \frac{\{1 - \exp[-hHt]\}}{hH}; \quad \eta = \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(gG + cC + iI)t]\}}{gG + cC + iI}; \quad \gamma = \psi\zeta gG(eE + \eta iI fF); \\ \zeta &= \frac{\{1 - \exp[-(aA + eE + fF)t]\}}{aA + eE + fF}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the obtained calculation relations allow us to synthesize a methodology for optimizing the process of recovering the ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations.

The sequence of decision-making according to the methodology.

The sequence of decision-making according to the methodology for optimizing the process of recovering ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations includes:

a) equal-intensity and equal-probability transitions of ME states in the conditions of carrying out combat operations from any state to any state are considered; the strategy of ME recovery under consideration can be used only in the case when any current state of ME does not depend on the state in which it was before that moment;

b) using the above equations (7)-(10), the indicators, i.e., probabilities that characterize the technical condition of ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations, are determined;

c) the intensities and probabilities (c, C) of the transition of ME to the state (P_O) of maintenance, as well as the intensities and probabilities (b, B) of its transition to the state (P_3) of intended use are determined and calculated;

d) the intensities and probabilities (g, G) of the transition of ME to the state (P_{II}) of preparation for use, as well as the intensities and probabilities (f, F) of its transition to the state (P_3) of intended use are determined and calculated;

e) the intensities and probabilities (i, I) of the transition of ME to the state (P_B) of recovery after damage, as well as the intensities and probabilities (e, E) of its transition from the state (P_{II}) of preparation for use to the state (P_B) of recovery from damage, that is, even before the start of the intended use of ME, are determined and calculated;

f) the intensities and probabilities of the transition of ME from the state (P_B) of recovery after damage to the state (P_3) of intended use, as well as the increase in the intensity and probability (h, H) of transitions from the state of recovery of ME after damage to the state of its combat use. It should be noted that the greatest attention should be paid to the study of the state

(P_3) of intended use of ME and the state (P_B) of recovery of ME after damage are determined and calculated.

This is due to the fact that these states of the ME recovery system and ME TC itself in the conditions of carrying out combat operations are the most important both in terms of the essentiality of recovery functions and the structure of unconditional links in the recovery system. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the conditions (terms) of the ME recovery, under which there is an increase in the intensity and probability of the transition of ME from the state (P_B) of recovery after damage to the state (P_3) of its intended use, as well as an increase in the intensity and probability (h, H) of transitions from the state of ME recovery after damage to the state of its combat use;

f) the terms of conducting recovery of ME are determined, according to which indicators of ME TC management, namely the coefficient of technical readiness K_{TT} and the minimax criterion E_{\min}^{\max} or P_{00}/P_{01} meet the specified conditions [2; 8-10].

The essence of the scientific novelty of the proposed method is that it takes into account the possibility of determining the optimal terms for the recovery of ME using the apparatus of a discrete Markov process in the form of a set of typical states of the recovery system, using the calculation ratios obtained in the model of auto-technical support for the process of recovery of automotive equipment, that do not coincide with the terms of its intended use in the conditions of carrying out combat operations. This will make it possible to develop on its basis practical recommendations for optimizing the recovery of ME at the expense of certain time reserves, and maintaining its serviceable state at a certain level.

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

An improved methodology for optimizing the process of recovery of ME in the conditions of carrying out combat operations, that, unlike the existing ones, using the apparatus of a discrete Markov process in the form of a set of typical states of the recovery system, takes into account the possibility of determining the optimal ME recovery terms, which does not coincide with the terms of its intended use in the conditions of carrying out combat operations, which makes it possible to develop practical recommendations on its basis as for improving the efficiency of ME TC management at the expense of determination of the rational composition of

repair and recovery bodies, defined and justified time reserves.

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